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Internet resources for teaching the English language

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Abstract: This article points to the advantages as well as disadvantages of the use of the Internet in a formal education context. Four upper secondary school teachers were interviewed face-to-face according to this theme. The various themes were identified in the interview. It includes general opinions on it and experience of the Internet, attitudes to teaching and learning, opinions on the use of the Internet planning and teaching resource, effects of the use of the Internet on students and teachers, and drawbacks of the use of the Internet in the school.

Keywords: multimedia, exclude, World Wide Web, Digital learning, text, image, video.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются преимущества и недостатки использования Интернета в контексте формального образования. Четыре учителя старших классов средней школы были лично опрошены по этой теме. В ходе интервью были выявлены различные темы. В них обсуждались общие мнения об Интернете и опыт его использования, отношение к преподаванию и обучению, мнения об использовании Интернета в планировании и преподавании, влияние использования Интернета на учащихся и учителей, а также недостатки использования Интернета в школе.

Ключевые слова: мультимедиа, исключение, всемирная сеть, цифровое обучение, текст, изображение, видео.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada rasmiy ta'lim kontekstida internetdan foydalanishning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari ko'rib chiqiladi. Ushbu mavzu yuzasidan to'rtta o'rta maktab o'qituvchilaridan intervyu olindi. Suhbat davomida turli mavzular aniqlandi. Ularda Internet haqidagi umumiy fikrlar va undan foydalanish tajribasi, o'qitish va o'rganishga bo'lgan munosabat, rejalashtirish va o'qitishda internetdan foydalanish haqidagi fikrlar, internetdan foydalanishning o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilarga ta'siri va maktabda undan foydalanishning kamchiliklari muhokama qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: multimedia, istisno, internet, raqamli ta'lim, matn, rasm, video.

Digital learning resources support information processing by helping students to develop mental representations through the mix of media elements presented to them. Digital learning resources include content and, sometimes, learning activities. They combine multimedia elements, including text, image, video, and audio, to

present information. Research on multimedia learning has demonstrated more positive outcomes for students who learn from resources that effectively combine words and pictures, rather than those that include words alone, Mayer [1,178]. Student attention and engagement with these resources helps them to process the information into working memory. When students meaningfully interact with the multimedia information, they encode this information into their long-term memory.

This meaningful interaction might involve learning activities within the digital resource itself or as a lesson that is created by the teacher. However, not all information presented in multimedia form supports learning. For learning to occur, the resources themselves need to be designed using sound educational principles and need to be purposefully integrated into the learning experience by the teacher. Educational theory provides direction for both the effective design of the resources and how a teacher can best use those resources with students. Cognitive load theory, developed by John Sweller [2,198], tells us that learning resources must be designed to reduce the load on our working memory in order for us to be able to construct a schema. Effectively designed digital learning resources:

1. Exclude information and activities that are not directly related to schema construction
2. Focus on information and activities that directly relate to schema construction
3. Clearly identify the complexity of learning materials and the experience of the learner.

These principles guide teachers in evaluating the digital learning resources that they might want to use with their students. Teachers can assess resources for how directly they cover the topic being taught, how clearly the information is conveyed, and how directly activities within the resources support student learning. And teachers can ensure that the lessons they design using these resources are also focused on the topic and take their students' abilities and experience into consideration. Teachers use digital resources for a variety of purposes and in many ways, including:

- As a way to introduce students to a topic
- As part of a teacher's lecture or demonstration
- As a stimulus to group or whole-class discussion
- To provide students with access to different text types
- To engage students in activities that are not possible in the classroom
- To allow students to work at their own pace as a review or extension activity.

Since the development of the World Wide Web in the mid-1990s, the ability to create, store, and share digital learning resources has expanded exponentially. Globally, significant effort has been put into creating collections, or repositories, of these resources, so that teachers can draw upon them for their lessons. In Australia, the national and state, territory governments have collaborated to develop digital learning resources that meet the content and learning objectives curricula for all stages of schooling. The National Digital Learning Resources Network (NDLRN) contains thousands of online curriculum resources that are made available to all Australian schools, free of charge. For more information, see the National Digital Learning

Resources website. Consider how digital learning resources can be used in teaching. Developing students' knowledge and skills related to ICT in the school years provides an important grounding for later in life. It also provides equity of opportunity, regardless of background. General social commentary and the popular press tend to generalise about young people, their access to and use of technology. Recent literature has challenged these assumptions and acknowledged that, although students today may have been born into a technologically rich world, they may not be avid and skilful users of technology. Further, there is recognition that merely providing access to technology is not enough.

Meaningful development of technology-based knowledge and skills is important for all students, in order to avoid a phenomenon known as the 'second-level digital divide', whereby people have drastically differentiated skills, which in turn influence how people participate in society. Society is just two reasons to use technology in education. Educators and researchers point to the potential of technology to increase motivation and engagement of learners, cater to different learning styles, and improve learning outcomes. When we talk about technology in teaching and learning, the word 'integration' is often used. The idea of integrating technology into the curriculum came about through a concern that we may have been teaching about and teaching how to use technology, but not addressing how students can apply technology-related knowledge and skills. To address this problem, there was a move to integrate technology into each key learning area.

With technology now being part of our everyday lives, it is time to rethink the concept of integrating technology into the curriculum and instead aim to embed technology into pedagogy to support the learning process. This means that technology becomes an integral part of the learning experience and an important consideration for teachers, from the onset of preparing learning experiences through to teaching and learning with students. The important role that technology plays in education gives teachers the opportunity to design meaningful learning experiences that embed technology. This is not a new area for teachers; we have always considered the tools and resources that can best support learning activities for students. However, advances and accessibility of technologies have made the possibilities seem almost endless. It is important not to use technology for its sake, but rather to embed technology appropriately. Here, teachers draw upon their expertise and experience in what to teach and how to teach it.

A teacher has many considerations and influences in designing learning experiences for students, and the appropriate use of technology is but one of those considerations. Just as teachers keep up to date with curriculum developments, new educational policies, and advances in the art and science of teaching practice, they keep up to date with the technological tools that are available to them. This means that sometimes experimentation and trial-and-error are just as important as experience in what influences teachers' lesson plans. The role and expertise of teachers are critical because teachers are at the front line of designing and delivering the learning experience. It has been well argued that just making technology available in schools does not mean that teachers will make use of the technology, nor will it necessarily

be used effectively [3,67]. This provides some ideas for teachers on how they can make meaningful use of technology in their teaching. Learning with technological tools. The following sections will serve to give an endless source of material for teaching and learning the English language. It has created a web for IBLL with several links to test the knowledge of the English language on various aspects

This shows the screenshot of the website. This website provides English language learners with various internet resources. The language learning materials for all levels of learners' knowledge are included. By clicking on links, learners can not only take different tests on various aspects of the English language with instant scoring but also get explanations. It also includes several useful internet resources, such as online dictionaries, games, a chat site, quizzes for defining the level of English language knowledge, etc. It also provides a standardized format for writing a letter of application and a CV.

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